

Digital technology in language teaching

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Annotation The purpose of this article is to look into the usage of digital technology in foreign language teaching.

Key words technology, digital, computer, mobile phone, online reading, and presentation tools

The theoretical foundation for the use of digital technology in the classroom is derived from diverse second language acquisition theories and classroom practices, rather than from any theory inherent in the technology. In other words, no specific educational ideas are suggested by the employment of any medium or technology, whether it be a chalkboard, a pad of paper and pencil, a telephone, or a computer.

Several studies show that digital technology improves both student motivation and teacher instruction in language learning. Similarly, using technology in English language teaching and learning may support the development of modern survival skills such as communication, teamwork, and information collection and retrieval.

Historically, the power of digital technology has been in providing means to mediate reading and writing. Online, there are vast numbers of real reading

much anything else may be shared on social networks. Although social networks have traditionally been used for non-educational purposes, instructors are increasingly using them to communicate with students because students are familiar with how they work and frequently visit these sites. There are two sorts of social networks: established networks like Facebook and do-it-yourself networks that supply the software for individuals to develop private networks. Instructors that utilize either sort of network do so to exchange information with students and to enhance student communication.

Listening skills. Faster internet connection speeds have dramatically enhanced the transmission of music and video files over the internet. This has expanded students' listening opportunities. There are websites dedicated to teaching listening in an ELT environment, as well as a wide range of podcasts, lectures, talk radio broadcasts, interviews, audiobooks, and other resources.

Pronunciation and speaking skills. One of the last areas to completely emerge has been the use of digital technology for pronunciation and speaking teaching. Part of this is due to the additional equipment required by older systems, including the necessity for sound cards and external microphones. To make matters worse, educational settings are not always conducive to voice recording, which is typically a solitary activity performed with one computer and one student. Because the solitary activity is not conducive to the group learning and interaction afforded by a classroom, instructors do not use this technology in class, and they do not assign it as homework unless they are certain that students have adequate access. The ubiquity of mobile phones, in particular, is transforming the face of pronunciation and speaking teaching. A telephone is a perfect device for these

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will be obsolete by the time the book or article is published. Some of the websites listed on the companion website for this book will most likely vanish, some of the software products mentioned will become obsolete, and businesses will be purchased and sold. Against this context, it is evident that textbooks and teaching materials are evolving at a rapid pace. With several forecasts of traditional textbooks being phased out and new approaches for electronic text creation and distribution emerging.

The expectation that computers will be a panacea for individuals attempting to learn a second language has not come true. However, it is obvious that digital technology may equip instructors and students with a new arsenal of tools for efficient language learning. Many learners find it stimulating to read on any topic and in every language available on the Internet, as well as to join in discussions with individuals from various spheres of life. Furthermore, the speed and scale of computers now allow massive databases to be handled, providing insights into language that we did not previously have access.

Mobile technologies, such as smartphones and tablet computers, have made it possible to integrate instructional technology into a variety of learning situations. The Internet provides numerous options for reading and writing in genuine settings, but it is not without flaws. For many, online reading is a slower, less in-depth experience than reading on paper, and online writing is vulnerable to plagiarism via copy-and-paste tactics. All educational technology use should be evaluated for effectiveness; we should constantly relate instructional technology decisions to the curriculum's goals and objectives.

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